

Swiss Institute of
Bioinformatics

Fostering gender balanced committees & scientific events

A brief checklist

SIB Diversity focus group (edi@sib.swiss)

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Why does it matter?

Because highlighting diverse role models helps break stereotypes and empower early-career researchers and aspiring scientists.

Because more diverse panels, committees, and events bring new perspectives, ideas, and networks, contributing to better science.

Because addressing the underrepresentation of women in such groups is one way to empower them in leadership roles, an ambition embraced by SIB and academic partners in Switzerland (e.g. [SNSF](#)) and abroad (e.g. [ELIXIR](#), [EMBO](#)).

Because overlooking these issues has risks, such as a drop out of speakers unwilling to take part, especially in all-male line-ups (e.g. [NIH's statement](#)).

[Read more](#)

Who should apply this checklist?

Organizers (SIB Employees or Members) of any SIB events featuring several speakers, or of committees, such as:

- panel discussions;
- speakers at conferences;
- scientific committees;
- workshops and tutorials;
- training courses.

What is the purpose of this document?

This checklist document is intended to enhance understanding among event and committee organizers about fostering diversity, particularly in terms of gender. It aims to highlight some of the challenges associated with achieving this goal, and it offers some practical advice on how to accomplish it.

In addition to gender, several other dimensions of diversity can be integrated to ensure that events are as inclusive as possible. For instance, consider school holidays, religious celebrations, or community events (International Women's Day, LGBTQ+ Pride, etc.) when choosing the date of an event.

Please let the Diversity focus group know how this checklist worked for you, if you found it useful, and how it might be improved in the future.

Checklist

- Make gender balance and diversity a priority early in the process of establishing an event or committee.

In the case of events, setting up a diverse scientific/organizing committee will help ensure the topic will be considered throughout the process.

- Define the desired proportion of women for the event/committee.

Consider your baseline representation when defining your goals: if the pool of targeted participants currently consists of only 25% women, achieving parity might not be realistic. But you could still aim for a more ambitious representation e.g. 30% to reach a beneficial critical mass and avoid 'token' representatives ([read more](#) on the topic of critical mass: EMBO report, page 11).

- When compiling the list of speakers/panelists/committee members etc. look beyond the usual suspects that come to mind e.g. consider early-career researchers.

If you are not able to identify a balanced pool of experts to contact, reach out to colleagues to ask for additional suggestions of candidates to add to the pool. The Diversity focus group can also help with suggestions.

- Invite women first, and only once most have answered, start inviting men.

Due to current imbalances in academia, women often receive many requests to participate as speakers/panelists/committee members. They might be more likely to decline than men. Increased diversity comes with challenges - but also opportunities, since speakers/panelists who decline, can always be asked to recommend others.

- Invite speakers/panelists based on their specific skills and/or expertise that prompted you to contact them in the first place and led you to believe they would be appropriate for your event.

Nobody likes to be a 'token' speaker and approached for reasons other than one's expertise.

If no women are able to attend or present at the event despite all efforts:

- . Consider rescheduling the event to a different time
- . If rescheduling is not an option, maximize other dimensions of diversity, visible or not: seniority, location, disciplines ...
- . Be prepared to communicate about the steps taken - *i.e.* to explain, if challenged, the lack of diversity